

Evaluation of 2LHERP in preventing recurrences of genital herpes

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The objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of a homeopathic complex in terms of intensity of attacks and duration of remission between attacks of genital herpes. Fifty three patients aged 18 or over with a minimum of four attacks annually were followed in this open multicentre study in a primary care setting. The principal parameters analysed were: frequency of attacks; intensity of symptoms, during treatment and/or after stopping treatment; treatment tolerance.

Eighty-two percent of patients treated for recurrent genital herpes benefited. In 41% of cases, there was no recurrence after the first treatment with follow-up of between 8 and 50 months. In 32% of patients, one or two relapses, in 9% of patients recurrences continued but with reduced frequency and intensity. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2000) **89**, 174–177.

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Introduction

Genital herpes is due to the herpes simplex virus, mainly of type 2. 10–20% of cases of genital herpes are of type 1. The illness is becoming more widespread: a recent study has shown that incidence has increased by 30% since the 1970s.¹ Over 20 000 cases are reported annually in the UK and 500 000 new cases annually are estimated for the USA.²

Various drugs have been tested as treatments for the acute phase and in the prevention of recurrences.^{3–7} To date, only the nucleoside analogue antiviral treatments, which block DNA synthesis (aciclovir and derivatives), have been shown to be efficacious. These drugs cause a significant reduction in the duration of the attack compared to placebo.⁸ Long-term treatment prevents recurrences,^{9–11} but they reappear on stopping treatment.³

In this open outcome study patients treated with the proprietary homeopathic complex 2LHERP were followed in order to evaluate its effectiveness in reducing the intensity of attacks and prolonging the remission between attacks.

Patients and methods

Fifteen primary care general practitioners in France and Belgium who are members of the 3IDI Institute agreed to participate in this post-marketing study. They recruited 53 patients aged 18 or over presenting with a minimum of four genital herpes outbreaks annually.

Ten patients had previously been treated with aciclovir but still had at least four attacks a year. Two patients remained on aciclovir and the test treatment in parallel. Patients with immune depression and pregnant women or those with a possibility of being pregnant were excluded. Diagnosis was made principally on clinical grounds, sometimes confirmed by serology.

The main criterion evaluated was frequency of attacks before and after treatment. Data on case history (previous frequency of attacks, serological confirmation of clinical diagnosis, duration and types of previous treatments) and treatment effect as well as any adverse effects were collected by doctors on the basis of interview of the patients when they attended for treatment or follow-up, following a pre-established questionnaire. Treatment was always started at the end of the acute phase of a herpes attack. Treatment was given for a minimum of 2 months as one capsule per day, the normal dosage for this treatment.

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2LHERP treatment (manufactured and marketed by Labo'Life España S.A.) consists of oral (sub-lingual) administration of a sequential (5 day sequence) homeopathic complex prepared in accordance with the European Pharmacopoeia norms and containing: deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA 8CH) salmon extract; ribonucleic acid (RNA 8CH); yeast extract; and synthesized oligonucleotides (SNA HER 1 16CH and SNA HER 2 16CH).

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the patient characteristics: sex, average age, frequency of outbreaks before the study, and case history. The previous frequency of attacks, the frequency of recurrence as well as the intensity of symptoms, during and after stopping treatment, were detailed for the 53 patients. Previous frequency was classified into three groups:

- four outbreaks per year;
- four to six outbreaks per year;
- more than six outbreaks per year.

Two patients did not return for follow-up and two incomplete case notes were rejected. The results were nevertheless calculated on the total number of patients

Table 1 Patient characteristics

		Mean
Number of patients	53	
Male	12 (23%)	
Female	41 (77%)	
Age	22-72	46 y
Previous frequency of outbreaks	Subintra to four outbreaks/y	5 weekly
Duration	6 months-25 y	8 y

Table 2 Characteristics of patients with good responses to treatment

Patient code	Treatment duration (months)	History	Previous frequency (outbreaks/y)	Duration of follow-up since last recurrence (months)	Antiviral
54	2	>1 y	4	9	—
69	2	5 y	4	8	—
4	2	>1 y	4 to 6	50	—
12	2	8-10 y	4 to 6	26	—
15	2	>1 y	>6	26	—
18	2	>1 y	4 to 6	39	—
49	4	6 months	4 to 6	30	—
51	2	3 y	4 to 6	22	—
56	2	1 y	>6	5	—
58	4	>1 y	>6	11	Parallel administration
59	12	5 y	>6	14	—
62	4	>1 y	>6	14	—
66	2	>1 y	>6	6	—
68	18	>1 y	4	Therapy continuing	—
70	4	>1 y	4	16	—
71	18	>1 y	4	Therapy continuing	—
75	10	6 y	>6	12	—
76	2	>1 y	>6	11	—
79	2	6-7 y	>4	10	Intolerance
82	4	≥10 months	4	14	—
89	2	6 months	>6	22	—
92	6	>1 y	>6	33	—

included at the start ($n = 53$). A recurrent attack was considered to be characterized by a herpes eruption. Prodromes were not considered to be a recurrence. We also collected secondary or undesirable effects during treatment.

Frequency of recurrences

Of the 49 cases where the information was accurately documented, we identified three distinct groups of patients, characterized as 'good', 'satisfactory' and 'poor' responses to treatment.

Twenty-two patients (41% of group) had good responses to treatment with no recurrence after starting treatment. Histories were very varied, pre-treatment attack frequencies varied from subintra to four attacks per year. Duration of treatment was variable dependent on the frequency and intensity history: Two patients had continuous treatment for at least 18 months; in three patients the length of treatment was 6-12 months; the remaining 17 had treatment for 2-4 months (mean = 2.6 months, Table 2).

The duration of post-treatment observation (except the two patients on continuous treatment) was 5-50 months (mean = 19 months).

One intolerant patient (patient number 79) and one resistant patient (patient number 58) to aciclovir are included in this group. After treatment of 2 and 4 months, respectively, the period without recurrence was 10 and 11 months. Patient characteristics for the very good responders are shown in Table 2.

Twenty two patients (41%) had 'satisfactory' responses to treatment: 17 patients (32% of the total sample) experienced between one and four relapses during the course of treatment and/or after stopping treatment, before prolonged remission occurred (Table 3), five patients (9% of the total sample) did

Table 3 Characteristics of patients with satisfactory responses to treatment

Patient code	Treatment duration (months)	History	Frequency history (no. of outbreaks/y)	Time to first relapse (disappearance = 0)	Maximum time without recurrence and without treatment	Antiviral
80	2	>6 months	>6	7 months then 0	5	Resistance
53	16	15 y	>6	15 months then 0	6	Resistance
65	4	4 y	>6	1 attack during treatment then 0	7	—
10	2	11 y	4 to 6	2 months then 0	9	—
63	2 then 2	18 months	>6	2 months then 0	11	—
8	6	1 y	>6	8 months then 0	12	—
55	8	20 y	>6	6 months then 0	12	Resistance
6	4	>1 y	4 to 6	15 months then 0	16	—
67	12	>1 y	4	5 months then 0	Treatment continuing	—
90	10	10 y	>6	4 months, 4 months, 4 months, 8 months then 0	8	—
7	8	>1 y	4 to 6	3 months, 1 month, 1 month, 4 months then 0	10	—
19	6	1 y	4 to 6	Several relapses, then 1 relapse at 12 months then 0	13	—
9	14	11 y	>6	Under treatment: frequency same, intensity reduced, then 0. After 3 months substantial outbreak then 0	14	Not very effective. Continued parallel
16	2	8 y	4 to 6	6 months then 18 months then 7 months, then =0	18	—
44	2	8 y	>6	12 months then 1 recurrence untreated then 0	23	—
52	6 then 12	12–18 months	>6	2 y then 0	Continuing treatment	Parallel
77	10	3 y	>6	Reduced frequency then 0	Continuing treatment	—
57	6	>1 y	>6	Reduced frequency and intensity	??	—
73	12	25 y	>6	Only during fatigue	Continuing treatment	Resistance
83	6	>1 y	>6	Prodromes—mini attacks 1 month in 2	9	—
78	6	1 y	4 to 6	Reduction in frequency and intensity	4	—
81	4 + 2 (on going)	1 y	>6	Reduction of frequency	5	—

not achieve total disappearance of recurrences but the frequency and intensity of attacks was clearly reduced.

Case histories were varied and frequency ranged from subintract to a minimum of four attacks per year. Four patients were on continuing treatment (from 10 to 18 months). Duration of treatment for the other patients in this group was between 2 and 18 months (mean: 7 months).

Duration of follow-up for patients no longer on treatment was between 5 and 16 months (mean: 9 months). For the six other patients duration of follow-up was between 8 and 23 months (mean: 14 months).

One patient had parallel aciclovir treatment: initially the intensity of the attacks diminished, then the relapses disappeared for 14 months without treatment. Four other patients whose genital herpes had not responded to aciclovir were also included in this group: in three the recurrences disappeared after a single relapse. The fourth had reduction in the frequency and intensity of attacks.

The characteristics of patients with satisfactory responses to treatment are summarized in Table 3.

Five patients had 'poor' responses to treatment (9% of the total sample); the treatment was judged lacking effectiveness—no modification in the frequency of attacks was observed. Of these five patients, two had had previous treatment with aciclovir (in one case lacking efficacy and in the other, intolerance). The characteristics of patients with poor responses are shown in Table 4.

Evolution of intensity of attacks

Of the 49 patients with fully document cases, 22 patients did not experience a recurrence (good response). The intensity of attacks was documented for all other patients. In five patients the treatment was judged to be without effect (poor response). All of the other cases followed (the 22 patients with satisfactory responses) showed a net reduction in the intensity of

Table 4 Characteristics of patients with poor responses to treatment

Patient code	Treatment duration (months)	History	Frequency history (no of outbreaks/y)	Time period to first recurrence (disappearance = 0)	Antiviral
86	12	>1 y	4	15 days, 15 days, 6 months then 4 months then outbreak every time product taken	—
80	4	2 y	>6	1 attack each time product taken	—
81	4	25 y	>6	No improvement	—
84	6	>1 y	>6	No improvement	Intolerance
85	2	1 y	>6	No improvement	Resistance

the recurrence(s) including cases of debilitating herpes and those resistant to other treatments.

Secondary effects

No secondary nor undesirable effects were reported by the treating doctors, even during prolonged treatment (18 months).

Conclusions

Nucleoside-type antiviral treatments are effective in resolving acute herpes attacks. They suppress recurrences or reduce their frequency during treatment but the outbreaks reappear on stopping the medication.

The study that we have carried out is focused on the long-term effect of 2LHERP. Some 82% of patients treated in this study for recurring genital herpes received substantial benefit in 42% of cases there was no recurrence after starting treatment, with follow-up between 8 and 50 months. In 32% of patients, a period of treatment was required before remission was achieved, after one to four relapses, sometimes after a long time period (up to 15 months). These relapses were generally of more moderate intensity.

In 9% of patients, complete disappearance of recurrences was not achieved, but frequency and intensity of attacks has been reduced. In the ten patients resistant or intolerant to aciclovir, 80% improved with 2LHERP. No secondary nor undesirable effects were reported by treating doctors, irrespective of length of treatment.

The results obtained suggest that more frequent administration (two to three doses per day) should be considered in patients not responding to treatment

within 2 months. Our results suggest that the homeopathic complex 2LHERP may have a useful role to play in the treatment of chronic genital herpes. A double-blind, placebo-controlled randomized clinical trial should be conducted to confirm these results.

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